

Manifesto for Agile Software Development

We are uncovering better ways of developing software by doing it and helping others do it. Through this work we have come to value:

Individuals and interactions

over processes and tools

Working software

over comprehensive documentation

Customer collaboration

over contract negotiation

Responding to change

over following a plan

That is, while there is value in the items on the right, we value the items on the left more.

agilemanifesto.org

Manifesto for Agile Teaching

We are uncovering better ways of teaching by doing it and helping others do it. Through this work we have come to value:

Individuals and interactions

over lesson plans and teaching tools

Learning effects

over learning documentation

Teaching and Learning collaboration

over teacher and learner roles

Responding to the individual situation

over following a plan

That is, while there is value in the items on the right, we value the items on the left more.

cf. agiledidaktik.ch//manifesto